

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF FORMING A PARTNERSHIP MODEL BETWEEN LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES AND CIVIL SOCIETY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the characteristics of establishing partnership relations between law enforcement agencies and civil society. It examines legal and informal forms of cooperation and ways to improve them. Special attention is given to developing organizational forms of cooperation as a strategic direction of law enforcement policy. Additionally, measures and key conceptual ideas that ensure effective cooperation have been identified.

Keywords: cooperation, law enforcement agencies, civil society, human rights and freedoms, trust.

Analysis of contemporary literature allows for the identification of several important aspects in implementing cooperation between civil society and law enforcement agencies. The nature of the dialogue between law enforcement agencies and civil society itself is intrinsically linked to the nature of these institutional structures.

Law enforcement agencies are an institutional component of the law enforcement system and, by their nature, embody the legal and political characteristics of the state. However, due to the diversity of methodological approaches to the concept of civil society, there is no single definition of it. On the one hand, civil society refers to any society composed of citizens of a state. On the other hand, only a society distinguished by certain features can be called a civil society. Such a society is characterized by the following new attributes:

Firstly, the main characteristic of civil society is manifested in its potential for self-organization and self-regulation.

Secondly, it is a society where free individuals and citizens are protected by law from pressure, interference, or uniformity imposed by various bodies, allowing them to freely express their capabilities [1].

Thus, civil society manifests as a "multifaceted, self-organizing, naturally formed system of social relations" and, by its essence, constitutes a sphere where private legal interests are expressed.

A system of specialized law enforcement agencies operates to protect the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens, ensure public order and safety, as well as effectively implement the protective function of law in the conditions of modern Uzbekistan.

It should be noted that achieving the desired state of law and order, as well as effectively implementing the tasks of law enforcement agencies in ensuring security, legality, law and order, and combating crime, is impossible without forming a model of constructive cooperation between civil society institutions and law enforcement agencies.

At the same time, despite the occasional inconsistency and even contradictory nature of these institutional structures' interests, both the state and civil society are interested in the effective functioning of public and state structures in the context of the democratization of

society's political and legal life. Therefore, for the modern state of Uzbekistan, the search for effective forms of cooperation with civil society is particularly important, especially in the field of law enforcement.

It should be emphasized that such cooperation is one of the important conditions for law enforcement agencies to effectively perform their duties, as well as serves to ensure the legality of these bodies' activities.

Thus, the issues of cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society are reflected in the normative legal acts regulating the activities of these bodies. For example, according to Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies," internal affairs bodies "cooperate with state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, and other organizations in the manner prescribed by law" in carrying out their activities [2].

Ensuring the implementation of criminal procedural legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, protecting the rights and interests of citizens, as well as increasing citizens' trust in law enforcement agencies, is one of the priority tasks of our time. We can see that the Ministry of Justice is responsible for implementing one such task in accordance with the Regulation "On the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan." In particular, according to the regulation, one of the ministry's functions is to ensure the widespread use of legal information by state bodies and organizations, coordinating their activities to effectively cooperate with civil society institutions and the media [3].

Therefore, cooperation and coordination between law enforcement agencies and civil society are of paramount importance in the implementation of law enforcement activities. This is because it is objectively difficult for specially authorized bodies to effectively fulfill their tasks without contact with civil society. Therefore, the joint comprehensive and coordinated activities of civil society and law enforcement agencies in protecting human rights and freedoms, ensuring law and order, legality and public security, combating crime and other violations will have a significant impact on increasing the effectiveness of the law enforcement system, as well as its development and improvement.

It should be noted that civil society is primarily interested in protecting its vital interests and ensuring a safe and stable environment. Therefore, the formation of constructive relations between law enforcement agencies and civil society requires not only legal regulation, but also the improvement of organizational forms of this cooperation.

In this regard, the improvement of organizational forms of cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society is one of the main strategic directions of law enforcement policy implemented by authorized and interested entities.

The tactical implementation of this strategic direction is inextricably linked to the consistent implementation of the following set of measures:

first, cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society in the formation of a unified socio-cultural space that includes common values such as humanism, justice, respect for law enforcement agencies and civil society. This process should ensure the harmony of social needs and personal interests.

secondly, holding joint events on legal awareness and legal propaganda among the general population. These measures contribute to raising the level of legal culture in society and reducing legal nihilism. For example, law enforcement officers can hold regular meetings with the population, organize online conferences on current issues, as well as create expert

councils on key areas of law enforcement activities. Particular attention will be paid to the legal views of legal scholars and the opinions of law enforcement veterans;

thirdly, the formation of favorable conditions for increasing the legal activity of citizens and creating opportunities to exercise the rights granted by the state. In this direction, it is necessary to transfer excessive or non-specific powers of law enforcement agencies to the level of local self-government bodies or public organizations, as well as to create effective mechanisms for monitoring the activities of law enforcement agencies by civil society;

fourth, strengthening citizens' trust in law enforcement agencies. This direction primarily involves ensuring the openness of law enforcement agencies, assisting them in combating offenses, as well as conducting preventive work with citizens prone to committing offenses. It is also important to eliminate corruption and reduce administrative barriers in the field of law enforcement.

It should be noted that the partnership model of cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society is formed based on the following key principles and organizational foundations. They reflect the nature, essence and strategic directions of this cooperation. Key principles include:

- respect for the rights and freedoms of a person and citizens,
- legality,
- openness and transparency,
- humanity,
- systematicity,
- objectivity,
- public trust and citizen support,
- the use of advanced technologies and scientific achievements.

The list of these principles is not complete or unchanging in content, as it is updated along with the development and complexity of forms of society's life.

At the same time, principles express a certain level of legal consciousness and legal culture and reflect the internal beliefs of the subjects involved in this process. However, each principle is based on the formation of a model of social partnership between law enforcement agencies and civil society and reflects existing mechanisms of cooperation.

In modern conditions, building partnerships between law enforcement agencies and civil society is accompanied by a number of challenges. Such problems include:

1. the lack of clear legislative mechanisms regulating cooperation between civil society and law enforcement agencies;
 2. insufficient level of legal activity of citizens;
 3. Low level of legal culture among the population;
 4. high requirements of civil society towards law enforcement officers;
 5. deformation of the professional and legal consciousness of law enforcement officers;
- the level of trust of civil society in the activities of law enforcement agencies is not always high.

Despite the existing problems in the organization and implementation of cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society, the state and society are interested in the joint implementation of important areas of legal policy in the field of law enforcement activities.

In the context of political, legal, and socio-economic reforms, the boundaries of state intervention in the spheres of self-organization and self-regulation of civil society and its expansion are becoming increasingly evident. It should be noted that the formation and development of civil society at the current stage of historical development is not a direct directive of state authorities, but the result of the increasing importance of local forms of collective life.[4].

Therefore, it is clearly evident that the priorities, goals, and objectives of law enforcement agencies and civil society coincide. These objectives include:

- increasing the effectiveness of the law enforcement system,
- carrying out law enforcement activities,
- ensuring law and order, security and legality,
- Effective fight against crime,
- achieving constructive results through social partnership.

Taking into account the above, the main conceptual ideas that define the essence of cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society can be defined as follows:

first, both civil society and law enforcement agencies are highly organized, complex systemic structures that have a large-scale internal structure, numerous blocks, subsystems and elements, and interconnected networks. This circumstance, on the one hand, complicates the collaboration process, but on the other hand, similar features contribute to the effective organization of joint activities.[5];

secondly, cooperation between civil society and law enforcement agencies is a process of interaction and change that is bilateral in nature. As a rule, civil society is considered to have the ability to control and limit state bodies in the process of such cooperation. But in reality, this cooperation is much more complex in terms of content and form;

thirdly, the development of a system of interaction between civil society and law enforcement agencies serves to increase citizen activity and foster a sense of social and legal responsibility.

fourthly, cooperation between law enforcement agencies and civil society is often informal, and the effectiveness of this cooperation depends on the level of participation of stakeholders in the protection of public order, ensuring public safety, combating crime, and preventive measures.

fifth, cooperation between civil society and law enforcement agencies is based on the principle of "feedback," that is, by accepting public opinions and suggestions and responding to them. As a result of such cooperation, the processes of self-organization and self-regulation of civil society will be strengthened.

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